

METHODOLOGIES FOR FORMING AN ECO-FRIENDLY MENTALITY

Kim Larisa Antonovna

senior lecturer of the Almalyk branch of the Tashkent State Technical
University named after I. Karimov, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract. The article presents a picture of the dependence of mentality on regional environmental factors. The processes of formation of environmental mentality, the patterns of influence of the mentality of the population, business, and government agencies on the emergence and development of environmental problems are analyzed. It is shown that it is the traditional mentality that is largely the cause of the emergence and escalation of conflict situations. The principles of consistent greening of the mentality of the population, business, and government bodies are outlined.

Key words: mentality, economy, environmental factor, human potential, natural resource, environmental protection measures.

Introduction. The mentality of the individual and society is an integral component of human potential [1; 2], plays an active, multifaceted role in the economy and social life. It determines the intellectual, professional abilities, mentality of the individual, the general intellectual level, the level of production skills of a particular social group.

Lately, “ecological factors”, regardless of the scale of localization, often mean only those that have arisen in modern man-made collisions between nature and civilization. That is, the term does not include physical-geographical, climatic, natural resource factors of the period preceding the industrial revolution and the emergence of the global anthropogenic pressure of the planet, many of which have survived in our time and which can be called factors of influence of undisturbed nature. However, it is methodologically more promising to classify as environmental not only the factors that

arose at the current alarming stage of the relationship between man and nature, but also those that existed in the early stages, far from global anthropogenic disturbances. Recently, the terms “ecology” and “ecosystem” have received exotically expanded interpretations (“ecosystem of thinking”, “ecosystems of banks and other financial and service organizations”, etc.). In our opinion, it is methodologically more useful to understand environmental processes without leaving the aspect of the relationship between man and nature (disturbed and not disturbed by civilization) and not to call ecological, ecosystem processes of internal (physiological, psychological, intellectual) human life or economic processes, organizational, business and other social activities that do not affect nature and do not depend on it.

We consider the division of ecological-mental tasks into the following tasks of analysis and synthesis to be a methodologically important classification:

- 1) analysis of the processes of formation of environmental mentality;
- 2) analysis of the processes of influence of mentality on the development of the environmental situation;
- 3) synthesis of an ecologized mentality (contributing to the improvement of the environmental situation).

The purpose of the article is, based on the results of the research, to develop a methodology for greening the mentality of the individual and society, a methodology for the synthesis of mentality that minimizes the contradictions of civilization and nature.

Literature review. The classic monograph on the influence of natural factors on the human mentality is the work of L. N. Gumilyov [3]. The author connects all human development with natural factors, especially highlighting the importance of landscape among them. L.N. Explaining the traditions and customs of peoples, based on the natural conditions of their place of residence, Gumilyov emphasizes that all peoples are original and unique due to diversity due to “landscape, climatic conditions, ethnic neighborhood, cultural traditions...” [3, P. 433], “the difference in ethnopsychological

stereotypes is determined by climate, topography, flora and fauna of ethnic places of development” [3, P. 474].

The second half of the 20th century became a time of deep awareness of anthropogenic environmental problems, problems of overload and destruction of the natural environment with civilization waste. A huge role in this awareness was played by the work of the Club of Rome, which traced the regional and global dynamics of the connection between production and environmental pollution from industrial and household waste [4].

A mass consumer society is mentally incapable of reducing production, of escaping humanity’s commitment to expanding its nature-destroying consumer demands.

Correcting this mentality, tragic for civilization, requires a deep systematic analysis of the real and artificial needs of man.

There are many different theories of needs in psychology and social psychology [5]. They are the basis for the development of methods for ecologizing mentality.

Throughout the history of mankind, environmental factors that determine the natural resources of the region have had a huge impact on the mentality and its dynamics[6].

Discussions on a global scale play a huge role in the formation of mentality, such as, for example, worldwide interest in the problems of climate warming due to the greenhouse effect, and in the problems of radical changes in transport infrastructure.

This review shows that civilization has entered an era of inadmissibility of ignoring environmental threats. At the same time, there is an understanding that overcoming contradictions is impossible without fundamental changes in the mentality of the individual and society.

Materials and methods. The main material for this study is the modern practice of the emergence, aggravation, and resolution of environmental problems. The main methods of accumulating materials characterizing mental-ecological interactions are familiarization with the development of socio-ecological-economic processes. At the

analytical stages, the main role is played by a systemic socio-ecological-economic analysis with a specific strengthening of the psychological and socio-psychological blocks.

Let us give an example of ecological-mental dependence. Stereotypes of behavior are clearly influenced by even the simplest spatial characteristics of the environment. These connections are very noticeable in the animal world. So, for example, for a steppe animal, the immediate reaction to danger is to run “without looking back” in any direction from the source of danger, and the first reaction of a mountain animal is to freeze and carefully search for a trajectory of safe movement. That is, the “geometry of the regional environment” is important for the formation of behavioral stereotypes. A person develops very different programs of orientation and movement in space, depending on the regional landscape. The physical characteristics that determine the climate of the region have an even stronger influence. Thus, many historians believe that the wars in North Africa and the Middle East have precisely climatic reasons, creating in the population a heightened sense of the lack of a comfortable environment, a militant mentality of constant readiness to win this comfort from others. There are more and more alarming forecasts that believe that as climate changes and land and water resources become scarcer, such an aggressive mentality will begin to spread to other regions. If we talk about the most powerful environmental factors that shape mentality, then in nature these are undoubtedly natural disasters. Scientific and technological progress in most situations is not able not only to resist them, but also to anticipate them in advance for the optimal organization of rescue.

Methods for studying the influence of mentality (formed, among other things, by environmental factors) on the national economy and environmental situation are also based on the general methodology of system analysis. The main difficulty in this case lies in the problems of predicting multidimensional, nonlinear processes of the natural environment’s response to anthropogenic influences.

The analysis of socio-ecological conflicts provides extremely valuable materials for the development of methodology. Today, there is not a single region of Uzbekistan

that has not been affected by environmental problems and caused intense mental contradictions in the “state – business – society” system.

Research results. Characterizing the results of applying the developed methodology with specific examples, we will begin with the processes of formation of mentality under the influence of environmental factors. Thus, the aesthetic parameters of the natural environment have a significant influence on the general mentality of man and society. Landscape plays an important role in the formation of various types of Russian mentality. It is interesting to note that the natural-aesthetic mentality has direct access to the economy. Thus, the reasons for the minimal production defects in Japanese enterprises operating on the same equipment as other countries is that a lot is decided by the increased “percentage of aestheticism” in the mentality of the Japanese - their souls are disgusted by ugliness, especially when created with their own hands. At the same time, the “aesthetic” mentality of the Japanese, which is largely determined by life among delightful landscapes, is purposefully shaped by the current education system. In Japanese elementary schools, there is a clear predominance of lessons on contemplating nature and its artistic reflection.

In solving environmental problems, certain mental elements play a key role, and they should be seen, systematically analyzed and formulated. Our research has developed a methodology for the thesis formulation of the mentality of society, which determines behavior in a particular environmental situation. The success of resolving ecological-mental conflicts directly depends on the accuracy of this formulation.

Let's move on to some results in the analysis of the influence of the mentality formed by various factors on the environmental situation. Let us dwell on the global problem of climate warming due to the burning of fossil hydrocarbons. The mental commitment to this type of fuel has two sides: firstly, the well-functioning and ease of use of the technology; secondly, the economic interests of producing countries. Both of these factors have combined to try to ignore the environmental problem. All over the world, lobbyists for increasing production and consumption are making attempts to lull environmental vigilance and even look for certain advantages in the ongoing

degradation processes. Thus, at first the rise in temperature itself was denied for a long time. When, as the observation network expanded, this became impossible, they switched to the position “Climate change is not anthropogenic, it is a safe natural cycle.” When it was necessary to admit anthropogenicity, a specific danger, and direct economic losses, some earthlings were encouraged by the thesis “The Northern countries will win more than they lose.” When life began to refute these calculations, all that remained was to criticize the excessive emotionality of the Swedish environmental activist Greta Thunberg.

No less complex manifestations of mental inertia arise in the process of diversification of the economies of extractive countries. Despite local successes, the exhaustion of the natural resource paradigm is too slowly and belatedly adjusting our mentality. It is difficult to penetrate into consciousness not only the thesis “The Stone Age did not end because the stones ran out,” but also those situations when, before our very eyes, “the stones are running out” (forests, fertile lands). The inertia of consciousness is quite enough to passively watch as the main life resources - clean water and air - melt away. This passive viewing concerns not only world problems, it is also characteristic of the regional, local level, of people’s attitude towards the environmental problems of their small homeland. Although there are more and more cases when the population shows indifference to the processes of destruction of the nature of their country.

Research shows that the green mentality today is primarily a mentality of thoughtful, economical consumption. In the 21st century The main reserve of sustainable development is the minimization of the artificial needs of civilization. However, advertising and aggressive marketing do everything possible to ensure that questions about the truth of the needs in the brain do not arise, much less be analyzed from a critical position. It is very important that both an adequately understood Maslow’s pyramid of needs and an adequately understood connection of this pyramid with the waste of civilization that is killing the planet are present in the mass consciousness.

However, even within the framework of non-artificial, basic needs, man is inclined to cause unjustified harm to nature. In Uzbekistan, 7 million tons of household waste are generated annually. Only 26% of them are recycled. The central key to escaping this madness is the greening of the mentality.

Moving from poverty and malnutrition to prosperity, people begin to waste food more intensively. It is known what a powerful leap China has made in improving the nutrition of the population. The country's leadership considers it very important to preserve the traditional mentality of thrift as a most valuable food resource. In August 2020, Chinese President Xi Jinping, through the Xinhua Agency, called on fellow citizens to exercise restraint in food consumption and waste.

The transition of society from “malnutrition in the stomachs” to “malnutrition on the plates” demonstrates a conscious anti-ecological choice. The individual and society are aware of both the problem of food resources and the problem of food waste, but have everyday motives to neglect these circumstances. The population of people who enjoy littering city streets and natural landscapes behaves just as consciously. Here we can also see a significant influence of the subconscious - an instinctive desire, by analogy with animals, to mark territory with waste products, asserting oneself and trampling on the rights of others to the marked space. A comparison can be made with Japan, a small area, where waste is not scattered, but carefully collected, processed and utilized in the construction of new island territories. Indeed, they dispose of them due to lack of space, but they do not scatter them, obeying their aestheticized mentality, as we discussed above.

In the methodology of greening mentality, the effective direction is the economic direction - when a person is proved by economic arguments that environmentally friendly behavior is beneficial and anti-ecological behavior is unprofitable.

Discussion and conclusion. Numerous regional-ecological problems of our time arise and are not resolved in any way, largely due to the traditional mentality of the population, business, and administrations. It is the mentality of the human consumer and the mentality of the mass consumption society that is steadily leading to

environmental disaster. Increasing efforts are needed to systematically green the mentality in the perception of world and regional problems.

Our tendency to ignore environmental threats is comparable in its psychological strength only to our tendency to environmental alarmism. And yet the first mental bias in today's situation is much more dangerous. Undoubtedly, the greening of mentality should occur without alarmist excesses, but it must be clearly understood that underestimating the degree of danger, as well as typical attitudes of outright misanthropy (“enough for our century”, “even after us there will be a flood”, etc.), creates the greatest danger –ness is the mentality of human self-elimination from environmental problems, the mentality of environmental fatalism.

At the same time, there is also a danger of mass disturbances and conflicts over environmental issues that destroy the rule of law. Lately they have been appearing regularly at various levels. Our research shows that the main reserve for optimizing regional environmental solutions is turning to the non-profit sector. In developing a methodology for resolving environmental conflicts, we come to the conclusion that the state and business should rely on social movements and non-profit organizations to a much greater extent than today.

In general, we can conclude that in order to maintain environmental and environmental-legal balance, immediate shifts in the mentality of the population, business, and government authorities are necessary.

On the other hand, despite the importance of developing an environmental mentality, this humanitarian component in itself cannot ensure the transition to sustainable development, since a “macroshift” in the consciousness of humanity is impossible. The main mechanisms for the transition to sustainable development are economic and legal mechanisms; an environmental mentality can only increase the effectiveness of their action.

References

1. Soboleva, I.V. Challenges for social policy in Russia: the need for a new model / I.V. Soboleva, T.V. Chubarova // *Economic science of modern Russia*. – 2017. – No. 3. – P. 55–69. – URL: <https://www.ecr-journal.ru/jour/article/view/37> (date of access: 09/2/2023). – Res. English
2. Fedotov, A. A. Human potential and quality of the population: approaches to determination / A. A. Fedotov. – DOI 10.24411/2500-1000-2020-10266 // *International Journal of Humanities and Natural Sciences*. – 2020. – T. 2, No. 3. – P. 79–86. – URL: <https://doi.org/10.24411/2500-1000-2020-10266> (access date: 2.09.2023). – Res. English
3. Gumilyov L. N. *Ethnogenesis and biosphere of the Earth*. St. Petersburg: Azbuka, Azbuka-Atticus, 2019. 672 pp.
4. Soboleva, I.V. Challenges for social policy in Russia: the need for a new model / I.V. Soboleva, T.V. Chubarova // *Economic science of modern Russia*. – 2017. – No. 3. – P. 55–69. – URL: <https://www.ecr-journal.ru/jour/article/view/37> (date of access: 08/28/2020). – Res. English
5. Forrester J. W. *World Dynamics*. Cambridge, 1971. 142 p.; Meadows D. H., Meadows D. L., Randers J., Behrens W. W. *The Limits to Growth. A Report for the Club of Rome's Project on the Pre-dicament of Mankind*. New York, 1972. 205 p.
- 6 Maslow A. H. *Motivation and Personality*. New York: Addison-Wesley, 1987; Kasser T., Ryan R. M. A Dark Side of the American Dream: Correlates of Financial Success as a Central Life Aspiration // *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. 1993. Vol. 65, no. 2. Pp. 410–422. DOI: 10.1037/2F0022-3514.65.2.410; DeCarvalho R. J. *The Founders of Humanistic Psychology*. New York: Praeger, 1991. 232 p.
7. Etkind A. M. The nature of evil. Raw materials and the state. *M.: New Literary Review*, 2020. 590 p.